

Checklist of the Phoridae (Diptera, Aschiza) of the Balkan Peninsula countries

Mario Langourov

National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria,
langourov@nmnh.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6756-3420>

Abstract: A total of 295 species of the family Phoridae (Diptera) belonging to 24 genera are presented from Balkan Peninsula countries, of which one genus (*Stichillus*) with one species is newly recorded from the region and two species are deleted from the list. Due to more intensive research, the largest number of species has been reported from Bulgaria so far – 230 of 23 genera.

Keywords: Balkan Peninsula, checklist, Diptera, Phoridae

Introduction

Scuttle flies (Phoridae) are one of the largest families of Diptera, with over 4500 described species in more than 280 genera (Disney, 1994; unpublished data), respectively the Palaearctic fauna up to now include more than 1100 species of 50 genera.

Although the first described species of a scuttle fly is from the Balkan Peninsula (*Musca festinans* Scopoli, 1763, Slovenia), and research in the area was quite active in the late 19th and early 20th centuries (thanks especially to Gabriel Strobl), there was subsequently a long period of stagnation in studies thereafter. Theodor Becker (1901) and Gabriel Strobl (1893, 1895, 1898, 1900, 1902, 1904) made significant contributions in these early stages, as also separate works by Ferdinand Kowarz (1873), Michael Funk in cooperation with Edoardo Graffe (1895), Eduard Fleck (1904, determined by Pius Sack), Joannes Thalhammer (1899), August Langhoffer (1919). Later, Herman Schmitz studied the rich collections of the Hungarian National Museum in Budapest and published the materials from them twice (Schmitz, 1924, 1953), also describing several new species. Unfortunately, all these materials were destroyed in 1956 when Soviet army troops suppressed the Hungarian revolution (Boros, 1957; Papp, 2016). In 1941 Robert Leruth published an article about cavernicolous scuttle flies in Transylva-

nia (Romania). In the 1950s, Ralph Coe of the Natural History Museum conducted two expeditions to the former Yugoslavia, during which he collected a significant amount of Diptera material, including numerous scuttle flies, which were identified by Charles Colyer. As a result, three articles are published, one of which contains a list of the identified species (Coe, 1956), and the other two contain descriptions of 12 new species (Colyer, 1956, 1962). More recently, in Romania, dipterologists Lucia Duşa (1970, 1974) and Corneliu Pârvu (2001, 2003, 2005) have published data on a number of species, almost all of which are outside the formal boundaries of the Balkan Peninsula. The author of this article has published several works on different areas of Bulgaria and Montenegro, paying special attention to the scuttle fly fauna of the Vitosha Mountain (Langourov, 2021). The purpose of this checklist is to systematise all available data scattered across a number of sources and to lay a solid foundation for further intensive research.

Material and methods

As a geographical term Balkan Peninsula fully encompasses territory of Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, mainland Greece, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia and partially Croatia,

Fig. 1. Map of the Balkan Peninsula countries. The territory of the Balkan Peninsula is covered with a grid.

Romania, Slovenia, Serbia and European Turkey. The northern border starts from the Danube Delta, follows the Danube River up to the Sava River with a north-west demarcation Sava-Krka-Postojna-Vipava-Soča, i.e. the border between the Alps and the Dinaric Mountains. For greater completeness and due to the lack of other sources of contemporary information about the countries, the checklist provides all information about the country, not just its territory,

which is a part of the Balkan Peninsula. An exception is made for Italy, of which a very small part falls within the Balkans and information is given only for that part. No scuttle flies have been reported from Kosovo and European Turkey so far, so they are not included in the work.

Genera and species are listed alphabetically. For all the species the text has the following format: species, synonym (only under which is reported from

the area), country (in alphabetical order), locality (town, area, district, mountain, etc.), author and year of publication. A question mark (?) indicates a not fully confirmed and therefore doubtful identification. The full list of synonyms of the species is not given, only those under which they have been published for the area. Data on the distribution of the species were retrieved from the Palaearctic catalog (Disney, 1991), including all the subsequent updates (unpublished data).

In older literary sources, a number of localities/settlements are given by their older names (most of them in Transylvania (from Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899; Schmitz, 1924, 1953)), and today they are known by different ones. Therefore, and to avoid constant repetition, they are given throughout the text by their generally accepted current names, and here their various variants are presented for reference:

Batrina = Bătrâna, Romania [Ialomita cave (Peștera Ialomiței)]
 Biharfüred = Stâna de Vale, Romania
 Bucsecs = Bucegi Mts [Munții Bucegi], Romania
 Carniola (Slovenian: Kranjska; German: Krain; Italian: Carniola) = Slovenia
 Csíkcsicsó = Ciceu, Romania
 Csíkszépvíz/Csík-Szépvíz = Frumoasa, Romania
 Felsőbánya = Baia Sprie, Romania
 Fiume = Rijeka, Croatia
 Görz = Gorizia, Italy
 Götzenberg = Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt [Vârful Măgura, Munții Cindrel], Romania
 Hammersdorf = Gușterița, Sibiu, Romania
 Hermannstadt = Sibiu, Romania
 Homoródfürdő = Băile Homorod, Romania
 Illyrien = Illyria – included western and central part of present-day Slovenia (Carniola), Slovenian Istria, northwestern Croatia (present-day Istria County and the Kvarner Gulf islands of Krk, Cres and Lošinj) and northeastern Italy (eastern parts of the Friuli–Venezia Giulia region, i.e. Trieste and Gorizia); because Schmitz use more precisely the terms “Krain”, “Görz” probably here he means part of present-day Croatian Dalmatian coast
 Kronstadt; Brassó = Brașov, Romania
 Küküllőszög = region stretching along the Târnava River in Alba County and Mureș County, Transylvania, Romania
 Laduscher Bergbäche gegen den Cindrel = Munții Cindrel, Romania

Laibach = Ljubljana, Slovenia
 Loitsch (Krain) = Logatec, Slovenia
 Meszes-Gebirge = Meseș Mountain (part of Apuseni Mts), Romania
 Meszes-hegység [Gebirge] = Meseș Mountains (part of Apuseni Mts), Romania
 Michelsberg = Csnădioara, Romania
 Montes Cibinienses = Sibiu Mts, Romania
 Nagyenyed = Aiud, Romania
 Novi = Novi Vinodolski, Croatia
 Orlater Bergwiesen = Vâlcan Mt, Romania
 Radnai havas [Radnai-havasok] = Rodna Mountains (Munții Rodnei), Romania
 Ragusa = Dubrovnik, Croatia
 Retezat-hegység = Munții Retezat, Romania
 Rétyi-Nyír = Reci, Romania
 Rotenturmpass = Turnu Roșu Pass, Romania
 Schulergebirge = Postăvarul Massif
 Siebenbürgen = Transylvania, Romania
 Szászka = Sasca Română, Romania
 Szászkabánya = Sasca Montană, Romania
 Székelyudvarhely = Odorheiu Secuiesc, Romania
 Verestorony (Vöröstorony) = Turnu Roșu, Romania
 Zimony = Zemun, Serbia

Results

1. *Aenigmatias franzi* Schmitz, 1950 – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Central Stara Planina Mts, Vitosha Mt, Pirin Mts (Langourov, 2009; Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt, Durmitor Mts (Langourov, 2009).
2. *Aenigmatias lubbocki* (Verrall, 1877) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Central Stara Planina Mts, Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2009; Langourov, 2021).
3. *Anevrina curvinervis* (Becker, 1901) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
4. *Anevrina thoracica* (Meigen, 1804) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021), Oso-govska Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997); Croatia: Velebit Mts (Langhoffer, 1919 as *Phora thoracica* (Meigen)), Rijeka (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).

5. *Anevrina unispinosa* (Zetterstedt, 1860) – Palaeartic-Oriental. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Disney, 1991.
6. *Anevrina urbana* (Meigen, 1830) – syn. *Aneurina setigera* (Loew, 1874) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: “Dalmatien” (Becker, 1901; Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b; Disney, 1991). Wrongly published for Romania under the synonym *Aneurina setigera* (Loew) by Schmitz, 1941b and Disney, 1991 – the locality in Schmitz, 1941b is “Walouiki, Rumänien”, which is Valuyki, Belgorod Region, Russia.
7. *Beckerina umbrimargo* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
8. *Borophaga femorata* (Meigen, 1830) – syn. *Hypocera flavimana* (Meigen, 1830) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mt (Schmitz, 1953), Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b); Croatia: Fužine (Schmitz, 1924b as *H. flavimana* (Meigen), 1928, 1929, 1940b); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1951); Disney, 1991.
9. *Borophaga irregularis* (Wood, 1912) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021).
10. *Chaetopleurophora bohemanni* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b; Disney, 1991).
11. *Chaetopleurophora erythronota* (Strobl, 1892) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), South Black Sea Coast (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b).
12. *Chaetopleurophora pygidialis* Schmitz, 1941 – Palaeartic. Romania: Dinu Island (Danube River) (Pârvu, 2005).
13. *Chaetopleurophora spinosior* Schmitz, 1938 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
14. *Chaetopleurophora spinosissima* (Strobl, 1892) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
15. *Conicera dauci* (Meigen, 1830) – syn. *Conicera atra* Meigen, 1830 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Odorheiu Secuiesc (Schmitz, 1953); Cluj; Bucegi Mts; Băile Herculane (Duşa, 1970 as *C. atra* Meigen).
16. *Conicera floricola* Schmitz, 1938 – syn. *Conicera minuscula* Schmitz, 1953 – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Târgu Ocna (Duşa, 1970 as *C. minuscula* Schmitz).
17. *Conicera schnittmanni* Schmitz, 1926 – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Bârsa Groşetului (Pârvu, 2001).
18. *Conicera similis* (Haliday, 1833) – syn. *Conicera pauxilla* Schmitz, 1920; *Conicera sensilipes* Schmitz, 1938 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1937; Schmitz, 1938 both as *C. pauxilla* Schmitz and *C. sensilipes* Schmitz); Schmitz, 1940a, 1940b (both as *C. sensilipes* Schmitz); Schmitz, 1952 (as *C. pauxilla* Schmitz and *C. sensilipes* Schmitz); Disney, 1991 (as *C. sensilipes* Schmitz); Greece: Disney, 1991.
19. *Conicera tibialis* Schmitz, 1925 – syn. *Conicera sobria* Schmitz, 1936 – Subcosmopolitan. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: near Dubova (Duşa, 1970 as *C. sobria* Schmitz).
20. *Diplonevra abbreviata* (von Roser, 1840) – syn. *Diplonevra sordidipennis* (Dufour, 1841) – Palaeartic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Zenica (Schmitz, 1953); Croatia: Karlovac (Langhoffer, 1919), Osijek (Thalhammer, 1899 as *Phora sordidipennis* L. [sic!]; Schmitz, 1953); Italy: Gorizia, Trieste (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1949); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b); Transylvania (Schmitz, 1949); Geoagiu-Băi, Cluj (Duşa, 1970); Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1924b); Disney, 1991.
21. *Diplonevra amphichaeta* (Schmitz, 1949) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997 as *Diplonevra lophochaeta* (Schmitz), misidentification; Langourov, 2021); Slovenia: Logatec (Schmitz, 1924b as *Dohniphora crassicornis* (Meigen), misidentification; Schmitz, 1953).
22. *Diplonevra concinna* (Meigen, 1830) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia (Nedelkov, 1912);

- Croatia: Bakar, Senj (Langhoffer, 1919), Istria (Schmitz, 1940b, 1949), Slavonia (Schmitz, 1949); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1949, 1953); Disney, 1991; Romania: Retezat Mt (Schmitz, 1953).
23. *Diplonevra crassicornis* (Meigen, 1830) – Westpalaearctic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Trebević (Strobl, 1898); Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Sljeme, Podsused, Bakar (Langhoffer, 1919); Romania: Băile Herculane, Orșova (Kowarz, 1873; Thalhammer, 1899), Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
24. *Diplonevra florescens* (Turton, 1801) – syn. *Diploneura florea* (Fabricius, 1794), *Diploneura abdominalis* (Fallén, 1823) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Bakar (Thalhammer, 1899); Italy: Gorizia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929); Disney, 1991; Romania: Băile Herculane, Orșova (Kowarz, 1873; Thalhammer, 1899), Sasca Română (Schmitz, 1924b).
25. *Diplonevra freyi* (Schmitz, 1927) – Westpalaearctic. Greece: Disney, 1991.
26. *Diplonevra funebris* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: West Danube Plain, Dobrudzha, Lozen Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Croatia: San Rinaldo Cave, near Sv. Mihovil Monastery, Istria (Pax, 1937; Schmitz, 1949); Disney, 1991; Greece: Disney, 1991; Romania: near Dubova (Duşa, 1970).
27. *Diplonevra glabra* (Schmitz, 1927) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
28. *Diplonevra lophochaeta* (Schmitz, 1927) – European. Italy: Gorizia (Schmitz, 1927, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1949). Wrongly published for the former Yugoslavia by Disney, 1991 – the locality in Schmitz, 1927 is situated in Italy.
29. *Diplonevra nitidula* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain, Ograzhden Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Greece: Corfu Island (Schmitz, 1924b as *Dohrniphora concinna* (Meigen), misidentification – Schmitz, 1953: “1924 fehlbestimmt als *concinna* von Corfu”; Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b); Disney, 1991; Romania: Bucegi Mts (Thalhammer, 1899 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *luctuosa* Meigen); Odorheiu Secuiesc (Schmitz, 1953); Ogra (județul Mureș) (Duşa, 1970); Comești (Pârnu, 2003); Penciu Forest [near Gostinu] (Pârnu, 2005).
30. *Diplonevra oldenbergi* (Schmitz, 1920) – European. Greece: Disney, 1991.
31. *Diplonevra pilosella* (Schmitz, 1927) – Palaearctic. Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1953).
32. *Diplonevra refulgens* (Schmitz, 1949) – Endemic. Croatia: Korčula Island (Schmitz, 1949; Disney, 1991).
33. *Diplonevra unisetalis* (Schmitz, 1935) – European. Bulgaria: South Black Sea Coast (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997).
34. *Dohrniphora cornuta* (Bigot in de la Sagra, 1856) – syn. *Phora chlorogastra* Becker, 1901 – Cosmopolitan. Bulgaria: North Black Sea Coast, Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2004b); Croatia: Dubrovnik (Becker, 1901), Pula (Schmitz, 1926), St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1938); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b; Disney, 1991; Cyprus: Cyprus Island (Schmitz, 1940b, 1951); Greece: Olympiaki Akti (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997).
35. *Gymnophora arcuata* (Meigen, 1830) – Westpalaearctic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Travnik (Strobl, 1898, 1900); Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Zagreb, Osijek, Božjakovina, Bakar, Lopača [= Dražice], Cirkvenica [= Crikvenica], Senj (Langhoffer, 1919), Zadar (Strobl, 1902, 1904); Greece: Disney, 1991; Italy: Trieste (Funk & Graffe, 1895); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Kitka Mt, Galichitsa Mt (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Băile Herculane, Orșova, Tășnad (Kowarz, 1873; Thalhammer, 1899), Sinaia (Duşa, 1970); Dinu Island [SW Ruse], Albina Island [S Chiselet] (Danube River) (Pârnu, 2005).
36. *Gymnophora integralis* Schmitz, 1920 – Palearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope

- Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Croatia: Illyria (part of Dalmatian coast with some of the islands) (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Disney, 1991; Romania: Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991.
37. *Gymnophora nigripennis* Schmitz, 1926 – Palaearctic. Romania: Albina Island [S Chiselet] (Danube River) (Pârvu, 2005).
 38. *Gymnophora quartomollis* Schmitz, 1920 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Albina Island [S Chiselet] (Danube River) (Pârvu, 2005).
 39. *Gymnoptera vitripennis* (Meigen, 1830) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 40. *Hypocera mordellaria* (Fallen, 1823) – Palaearctic. Romania: Băile Herculane, Orșova (Kowarz, 1873; Thalhammer, 1899), region stretching along the Târnava River, Orșova (Schmitz, 1924b), Berbești (Pârvu, 2003); former Yugoslavia: Disney, 1991.
 41. *Megaselia abdita* Schmitz, 1959 – Holarctic, introduced to St. Helena Island (Afrotropical Region). Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).
 42. *Megaselia abernethae* Disney, 1988 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 43. *Megaselia abludens* Schmitz, 1927 – European. Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1927); Disney, 1991.
 44. *Megaselia aculeata* (Schmitz, 1919) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
 45. *Megaselia aequalis* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Oteshevo (Coe, 1956; Langourov, 1999); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957); Disney, 1991.
 46. *Megaselia affinis* (Wood, 1909) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 47. *Megaselia albicans* (Wood, 1908) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 48. *Megaselia albicaudata* (Wood, 1910) – Holarctic-Afrotropical. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
 49. *Megaselia albiclava* Schmitz, 1926 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 50. *Megaselia albocingulata* (Strobl, 1906) – syn. *Aphiochaeta languescens* (Schmitz, 1924) – Mediterranean. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Novi [= Novi Vinodolski] (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a as *A. languescens* Schmitz); Schmitz, 1958; Schmitz & Delage, 1974; Greece: Disney, 1991.
 51. *Megaselia alticolella* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b).
 52. *Megaselia altifrons* (Wood, 1909) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965b); Romania: Orșova (Schmitz, 1924b).
 53. *Megaselia analis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – syn. *Aphiochaeta fuscinula* Schmitz, 1926 – European. Romania: Plasa Tileagd: Vârciorog, Pesterea dela Surducel; Plasa Vascau: Fânatze, Pesterea dela Fânatze; Băitza, Pesterea dela Varnitza, Pesterea dela Păretzii Corlatului; Sighistel, Pesterea de sus dela Corbesti, Pestera dela Corbasta (Leruth, 1941 as *M. fuscinula* (Schmitz)); Schmitz, 1941a; Disney, 1991 (both as *M. fuscinula* (Schmitz)).
 54. *Megaselia angusta* (Wood, 1909) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
 55. *Megaselia angustiata* Schmitz, 1936 – syn. *Megaselia ultrabrevis* Schmitz, 1937 – Mediterranean. Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1937 as *M. ultrabrevis* Schmitz).
 56. *Megaselia annulipes* (Schmitz, 1921) – Holarctic. Romania: Comana, Vlașca (Schmitz, 1921; 1958b; Disney, 1991); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a.

57. *Megaselia aquilonia* Schmitz, 1958 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
58. *Megaselia basispinata* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Holarctic-Neotropical. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957a).
59. *Megaselia beatricis* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: “Rakovo Dolina” = Rakov Škocjan (Colyer, 1962; Disney, 1991).
60. *Megaselia beckeri* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
61. *Megaselia berndseni* (Schmitz, 1919) – syn. *Megaselia pygmaeoides* (Lundbeck, 1921) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Greece: Crete Island (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a); North Macedonia: Oteshevo, Galichitsa Mt (Coe, 1956 as *M. pygmaeoides* (Lundbeck)), Suva Gora Mt (Matka) (Langourov, 1999). Wrongly published for Bulgaria by Disney, 1991 – the locality in Coe, 1956 is situated in North Macedonia.
62. *Megaselia bovista* (Gimmerthal, 1848) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
63. *Megaselia brevicostalis* (Wood, 1910) – Holarctic-Neotropical. Bulgaria: Varshets, Western Stara Planina Mts (Schmitz, 1953), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004c), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Oteshevo (Coe, 1956), Baba Mt (Langourov, 1999); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
64. *Megaselia brevior* (Schmitz, 1924) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); North Macedonia: Suva Gora Mt (Matka) (Langourov, 1999).
65. *Megaselia brevissima* (Schmitz, 1924) – Mediterranean. Croatia: Plitvice Lakes (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991).
66. *Megaselia breviterga* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Disney, 1991; Romania: Băile Homorod (Schmitz, 1953).
67. *Megaselia brunneicornis* (Schmitz, 1920) – European. Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Disney, 1991.
68. *Megaselia brunneipennis* Costa, 1857 – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
69. *Megaselia campestris* (Wood, 1908) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Braşov (Schmitz, 1924b); Liuborajdia, near Danube River (Duşa, 1970); Pasul Prislop; Târgu Ocna, Valea Uzului (Duşa, 1974); Bârsa Groşetului (Pârvu, 2001); Disney, 1991.
70. *Megaselia ciliata* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Bosnia-Herzegovina: Krbljina/ Hrbljina Mt (Strobl, 1898, 1900); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Bucegi Mts, Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895); Bucegi Mts, Sibiu Mt (Thalhammer, 1899), Meseş Mt (part of Apuseni Mountains (Schmitz, 1924b).
71. ? *Megaselia cinereifrons* (Strobl, 1910) – European. Greece: Disney, 1991 (“GH”).
72. *Megaselia cirricauda* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Schmitz & Delage, 1974; Disney, 1991).
73. *Megaselia claricornis* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Disney, 1991).
74. *Megaselia coei* Schmitz, 1938 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
75. *Megaselia collini* (Wood, 1909) – West-palaeartic. Romania: Frumoasa, ? Orşova (Schmitz, 1924b).
76. *Megaselia communiformis* (Schmitz, 1918) – Westpalaeartic. Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b).
77. *Megaselia conformis* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
78. *Megaselia consetigera* (Schmitz, 1925) – European. North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Băile Homorod (Schmitz, 1953); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1974).

79. *Megaselia constricta* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Disney, 1991).
80. *Megaselia costalis* (von Roser, 1840) – European. Croatia: Brušane/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Disney, 1991; Romania: Orșova (Schmitz, 1924b).
81. *Megaselia crassicosta* (Strobl, 1892) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Gura Râului (Pârnu, 2001).
82. *Megaselia crassilla* Schmitz, 1926 – European. Romania: Odorheiu Secuiesc (Schmitz, 1953 as *M. crassila* [sic!] Schmitz).
83. *Megaselia crassipes* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
84. *Megaselia criniticauda* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Schmitz & Delage, 1974; Disney, 1991).
85. *Megaselia curvicapilla* Schmitz, 1947 – West-palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); North Macedonia: Baba Mt (Langourov, 1999).
86. *Megaselia dahli* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999).
87. *Megaselia deltomera* (Schmitz, 1924) – Euro-Mediterranean. Croatia: Novi Vinodolski (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1958a; Disney, 1991).
88. *Megaselia densior* Schmitz, 1927 – European. Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
89. *Megaselia differens* Schmitz, 1948 – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); North Macedonia: Baba Mt (Langourov, 1999).
90. *Megaselia discreta* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991).
91. *Megaselia diversa* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004c), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Sveto Brdo [Selsko Brdo, Šestak Brdo]/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b), Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965a; Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
92. *Megaselia dubitalis* (Wood, 1908) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
93. *Megaselia eccoptomera* Schmitz, 1927 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
94. *Megaselia elongata* (Wood, 1914) – syn. *Aphiochaeta cuspidata* Schmitz, 1919 – West-palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b as *A. cuspidata* Schmitz); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a (as *Plastophora elongata* (Wood)); Disney, 1991; Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b as *A. cuspidata* Schmitz), Gura Râului (Pârnu, 2001).
95. *Megaselia emarginata* (Wood, 1908) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
96. *Megaselia errata* (Wood, 1912) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b).
97. *Megaselia fenestralis* (Schmitz, 1919) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Varshets/Western Stara Planina Mts (Schmitz, 1953), Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).
98. *Megaselia filamentosa* Schmitz, 1958 – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
99. *Megaselia flava* (Fallen, 1823) – Holarctic-Oriental. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Grab/Sutjeska/Maglić Mt, Krbljina/ Hrbljina Mt (Strobl, 1898); Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999), Galichitsa Mt (Coe, 1956); Romania: Bucegi Mts (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899), Orșova (Schmitz, 1953).
100. *Megaselia flavescens* (Wood, 1909) – European. Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b), Târgu

- Ocna, Valea Uzului; Slănic-Moldova; Ceahlău, Schitul Durău (Duşa, 1974).
101. *Megaselia flavicans* Schmitz, 1935 – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001); Croatia: Brušane/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. flava* (Fallen); Schmitz, 1953); Greece: Corfu (Schmitz, 1935b); Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Galichitsa Mt (Coe, 1956); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. flava* (Fallen); Schmitz, 1953); Cluj (Duşa, 1970); Gura Râului (Pârnu, 2001).
 102. *Megaselia flavicoxa* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Bucegi Mts (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899), Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
 103. *Megaselia floccicauda* Disney, 2006 – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Ograzhden Mt (Disney & Lapeva-Gjonova, 2011).
 104. *Megaselia frameata* Schmitz, 1927 – syn. *Megaselia imberbis* Schmitz, 1934 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Huta, Cluj District (Duşa, 1974 as *M. imberbis* Schmitz).
 105. *Megaselia frontalis* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1953).
 106. *Megaselia fungivora* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 107. *Megaselia fusca* (Wood, 1909) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Temnata Dupka Cave/Western Stara Planina Mts (Czerny, 1930), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001; Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004c); Bosnia-Herzegovina: Schmitz, 1928, 1929; Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
 108. *Megaselia fusciclava* Schmitz, 1935 – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).
 109. *Megaselia fuscipalpis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 110. *Megaselia fuscovariana* Schmitz, 1933 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 111. *Megaselia giraudii* (Egger, 1862) – syn. *Megaselia rata* (Collin in Wood, 1908) – Holarctic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Suha/Sutjeska/Maglić Mt (Strobl, 1898, 1900); Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. rata* (Collin)), Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Schmitz, 1928, 1929 (as *M. rata* (Collin)), Schmitz, 1941a; Disney, 1991; Greece: Corfu (Schmitz, 1924b); North Macedonia: Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Romania: Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt, Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895), Sibiu Mt (Thalhammer, 1899 as *Phora Giremdii* [sic!] Egger), Braşov, Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. rata* (Collin)), Târgu Ocna, Valea Uzului (Duşa, 1974); Gura Râului (Pârnu, 2001); Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. rata* (Collin)).
 112. *Megaselia glabrifrons* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 113. *Megaselia gregaria* (Wood, 1910) – European (introduced to Australia, Australasian/Oceanian Region). Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 114. *Megaselia halterata* (Wood, 1910) – Sub-cosmopolitan. Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mts, Sofia Plain, Vitosha Mt, Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2001, 2004b, 2004c, 2021); Romania: Dubova, Berzasca (Duşa, 1970).
 115. *Megaselia hirsuta* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 116. *Megaselia hirticaudata* (Wood, 1910) – syn. *Megaselia capronata* Schmitz, 1940 – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a as *M. capronata* Schmitz).
 117. *Megaselia hirticrus* (Schmitz, 1918) – Palaeartic. Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965a).
 118. *Megaselia hirtiventris* (Wood, 1909) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).
 119. *Megaselia horsfieldi* Disney, 1986 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
 120. *Megaselia humeralis* (Zetterstedt, 1838) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b).

121. *Megaselia hyalipennis* (Wood, 1912) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: “?; Plasa Vascău: Băitza, Pesterea dela Varnitza” (Leruth, 1941).
122. *Megaselia hypopygialis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Retezat Mts (Schmitz, 1924b).
123. *Megaselia indifferens* (Lundbeck, 1920) – European. Croatia: Brušane/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1974; Disney, 1991); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
124. *Megaselia infraposita* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
125. *Megaselia intonsa* Schmitz, 1948 – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
126. *Megaselia involuta* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Greece: Crete Island, Greece (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Delage, 1974; Disney, 1991; Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Delage, 1974); Disney, 1991).
127. *Megaselia largifrontalis* Schmitz, 1939 – Holarctic-Afrotropical. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021).
128. *Megaselia lata* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Reci (Schmitz, 1953); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
129. *Megaselia latericia* Schmitz, 1935 – European. Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1935a; Disney, 1991).
130. *Megaselia latifemorata* (Becker, 1901) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak, Mošunje (Schmitz, 1924b); Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b), Stâna de Vale (Schmitz, 1953).
131. *Megaselia latifrons* (Wood, 1910) – syn. *Megaselia propior* Colyer, 1956 – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Rila monastery/Rila Mts (Schmitz, 1953), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Oteshevo/Galichitsa Mt, Prespa Lake (Colyer, 1956; Coe, 1956; Disney, 1991; Langourov, 1999 all under the synonym *Megaselia propior* Colyer).
132. *Megaselia latipalpis* (Schmitz, 1921) – European. Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
133. *Megaselia ledburiensis* (Brues, 1915) – syn. *Megaselia subfuscipes* Schmitz, 1935 – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010 as *M. subfuscipes* Schmitz); Greece (Disney, 1991 as *M. subfuscipes* Schmitz).
— *Megaselia leucozona* Schmitz, 1930 – Mediterranean. Wrongly published for Greece in the Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera (Disney, 1991), see Polidori et al, 2005: “...*M. leucozona* Schmitz, previously only known from a single female from Daghestan”.
134. *Megaselia longicostalis* (Wood, 1912) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Predbalkan Mts, Central Stara Planina Mts, Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2001; Langourov, 2004c), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
135. *Megaselia longipalpis* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaearctic. North Macedonia: Galichitsa Mt/Prespa Lake (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1999.
136. *Megaselia longiseta* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
137. *Megaselia lucifrons* (Schmitz, 1918) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
138. *Megaselia lutea* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Zagreb (Langhoffer, 1919); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Galichitsa Mt/Ohrid Lake (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1999.
139. *Megaselia luteipes* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991.

140. *Megaselia lutescens* (Wood, 1910) – European. Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
141. *Megaselia mallochi* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
142. *Megaselia manicata* (Wood, 1910) – West-palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Montenegro (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1958); North Macedonia: Prespa Lake (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1991; Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1958); Disney, 1991.
143. *Megaselia meconicera* (Speiser, 1925) – Holarctic. Albania: Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957; Disney, 1991; Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
144. *Megaselia meigeni* (Becker, 1901) – Palaearctic. Albania: Disney, 1991; Greece: Korfu Island (Becker, 1901; Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Delage, 1981); Disney, 1991.
145. *Megaselia melanocephala* (von Roser, 1840) – Euro-Mediterranean. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Romania: Reg. Oltenia, Peștera Vacilor din Steiul Orzeștilor (Decu-Burghete, 1963).
146. *Megaselia minor* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – syn. *Megaselia angustifrons* (Wood, 1912) – West-palaearctic. Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956 as *M. angustifrons* (Wood)); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Frumoasa (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. angustifrons* (Wood)), Târgu Ocna, Valea Uzului (Dușa, 1974); Gura Râului (Pârvu, 2001).
147. *Megaselia minuta* (Aldrich, 1892) – syn. *Megaselia luminosa* Schmitz, 1952 – Holarctic. North Macedonia: Ohrid Lake (Coe, 1956 as *M. luminosa* Schmitz); Langourov, 1999.
148. *Megaselia mixta* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
149. *Megaselia nasoni* (Malloch, 1914) – syn. *Megaselia coaequalis* (Schmitz, 1919) – Holarctic. Croatia: Brušane/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. coaequalis* (Schmitz)); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957a; Disney, 1991; Romania: M-ții Călimani, V. Lomaș (Dușa, 1974 as *M. coaequalis* (Schmitz)).
150. *Megaselia nigra* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Bulgaria (Choleva, 1964); Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1999; Romania: Bucegi Mts (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899 both as *Phora pulicaria* var. *nigra* Meigen).
151. ? *Megaselia nigrescens* (Wood, 1910) – European. North Macedonia: Prespa Lake (Coe, 1956, under question mark; needs confirmation); Langourov, 1999.
152. *Megaselia nigriceps* (Loew, 1866) – syn. *Megaselia projecta* (Becker, 1901) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Bulgaria (Schmitz, 1953 as *M. projecta* (Becker)), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Schmitz, 1957a (as *M. projecta* (Becker)); Disney, 1991; Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956 as *M. projecta* (Becker)), Brušane/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b as *M. projecta* (Becker)); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957a (as *M. projecta* (Becker)); Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Serbia: Tmušnica pećina, Boljare (Séguy, 1963, as *Phora bicolor* Zetterstedt).
153. *Megaselia nigripalpis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
154. *Megaselia oblongifrons* Schmitz, 1939 – European. North Macedonia: Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1999.
155. *Megaselia obscuripennis* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b).
156. *Megaselia oxybelorum* Schmitz, 1928 – syn. *Megaselia insecta* Schmitz, 1953 – West-palaearctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Schmitz, 1953 as *M. insecta* Schmitz), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Băile Homorod (Schmitz, 1953; Disney, 1991 both as *M. insecta* Schmitz).
157. *Megaselia palmeni* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Gura Râului (Pârvu, 2001).
158. *Megaselia parva* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956).
159. *Megaselia pectinifera* Schmitz, 1926 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
160. *Megaselia pectoraliformis* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Schmitz & Delage, 1981; Disney, 1991).

161. *Megaselia pectoralis* (Wood, 1910) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Băile Homorod (Schmitz, 1953), Tulgheș (Harghita); Dealul Ștefăniței (Bistrița-Năsăud) (Dușa, 1974); Disney, 1991.
162. *Megaselia pectorella* Schmitz, 1929 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
163. *Megaselia pedatella* (Schmitz, 1926) – syn. *Megaselia rara* Colyer, 1962 – European. North Macedonia: Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Colyer, 1962; Disney, 1991 both as *M. rara* Colyer; Disney, 2003); Langourov, 1999 as *M. rara* Colyer.
164. *Megaselia perdistans* (Schmitz, 1924) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
165. *Megaselia perfusca* Schmitz, 1935 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
166. *Megaselia picta* (Lehmann, 1822) – syn. *Megaselia interrupta* (Zetterstedt, 1838) – Sub-cosmopolitan. Romania: Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899 both as *M. interrupta* (Zetterstedt)), Orșova (Schmitz, 1924b).
167. *Megaselia piliventris* Schmitz, 1937 – Palaeartic-Afrotropical. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999 as *M. cirriventris* Schmitz), Galichitsa Mt/Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Schmitz, 1958a; Disney, 1991 both as *M. cirriventris* Schmitz.
168. *Megaselia pleuralis* (Wood, 1909) – Sub-cosmopolitan species with Holarctic origin. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Herzegovina (Schmitz, 1919, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957a); Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mts (Czerny, 1930), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001, 2021), Central Stara Planina Mts, Sofia Plain, Western Rhodope Mts, Eastern Rhodope Mts, Derventski Hills, Strandzha Mt (Langourov, 2001, 2004c, 2010); Schmitz, 1957a; Disney, 1991; Croatia: Spilja Ostaševica (cave)/Mljet Island (Schmitz, 1919); Schmitz, 1953, 1957a (“Dalmatien”); Disney, 1991; Greece: “Grotte de l’Apano Skala, pres de l’abattoir de Naousa”, Naousa (Séguy, 1963); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999), Galichitsa Mt/Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Romania: “Plasa Alesd: Călatzea, Pesterea [cave] dela Cuglis” [Călățea, Comuna Aștileu, Bihor] (Leruth, 1941), Târgu Ocna, Valea Uzului; Borsec (Dușa, 1974); Disney, 1991; Serbia: Pečina (cave) near Jabuka, Bijeli Krs (Séguy, 1963).
169. *Megaselia plurispinulosa* (Zetterstedt, 1860) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Greece: Corfu Island (Schmitz, 1924b as *Aphiochaeta Giraudii* Schmitz nec (Egger); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Delage, 1974); Disney, 1991; Italy: Gorizia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a); North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999), Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Romania: Odorheiu Secuiesc (Schmitz, 1953); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1924b as *A. Giraudii* Schmitz nec (Egger); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
170. *Megaselia posticata* (Strobl, 1898) – West-palaeartic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Bosnia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Dubrovnik (Strobl, 1898, 1900; Disney, 1991); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957a (“Dalmatien”); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1957a).
171. *Megaselia praeacuta* (Schmitz, 1919) – syn. *Megaselia arietina* Disney in Čakar & Disney, 1991 – Westpalaeartic. Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1937, “?”); North Macedonia: Skopje (Čakar & Disney, 1991 as *M. arietina* Disney), Dihovo (Kiprijanovska et al., 2019); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
172. *Megaselia producta* (Schmitz, 1921) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004c).
173. *Megaselia propinqua* (Wood, 1909) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Western Stara planina Mts, Varshets (Schmitz, 1953), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1924b).
174. *Megaselia protarsalis* Schmitz, 1927 – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).

175. *Megaselia pseudogiraudii* (Schmitz, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: “Slavonien” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a), Istria (Schmitz, 1941a); Schmitz & Delage, 1974; Disney, 1991.
176. *Megaselia pulicaria* (Fallen, 1823) – Holarctic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Mostar, Trebinje (Strobl, 1898), Čevljanovići/near Sarajevo (Strobl, 1902, 1904); Bulgaria: Western Stara planina Mts, Varshets (Schmitz, 1953); Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1938), Zadar (Strobl, 1902, 1904), Hvar (Strobl, 1893, 1898); Disney, 1991; Italy: Nabrežina/Aurisina (Funk & Graffe, 1895); Romania: Bucegi Mts (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899), Azuga (Fleck, 1904), Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b), Gura Râului (Pârnu, 2001).
177. *Megaselia pullipalpis* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Disney, 1991).
178. *Megaselia pumila* (Meigen, 1830) – syn. *Megaselia atripes* (Brues, 1915) – Palaearctic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Jablanica (Strobl, 1898 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *pumila*); Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Gospić (Schmitz, 1924b as *Aphiochaeta atripes* Brues), Zadar (Strobl, 1902, 1904 both as *P. pulicaria* var. *pumila*); Schmitz, 1928, 1929; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965a; Disney, 1991; Italy: Gorizia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Shar Mts, Baba Mt (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Bucegi Mts, Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt, Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895); Sibiu Mt (Thalhammer, 1899), Ciceu (Schmitz, 1953).
179. *Megaselia pusilla* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Romania: Băile Homorod (Schmitz, 1953); Serbia: Morović (Coe, 1956); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a).
180. *Megaselia pygmaea* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – syn. *Megaselia brachyneura* (Egger, 1862) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899 both as *Phora brachyneura* (Egger)), Odorheiu Secuiesc (Schmitz, 1953 as *M. brachyneura* (Egger)), Gura Râului (Pârnu, 2001); Serbia: Zemun (Schmitz, 1924b as *Aphiochaeta brachyneura* (Egger) and *A. pygmaea* (Zetterstedt)); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928).
181. *Megaselia quadriseta* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Bulgaria: Pazardzhik/Trakia Lowland (Georgiev & Langourov, 1997).
182. *Megaselia robusta* Schmitz, 1928 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
183. *Megaselia rubella* (Schmitz, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Romania: Turnu Roșu (Schmitz, 1924b).
184. *Megaselia ruficornis* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Zagreb, Senj (Langhoffer, 1919), Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b), Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Delage, 1981; Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Mehadia, Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b).
185. *Megaselia rufifrons* (Wood, 1910) – European. Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
186. *Megaselia rufipes* (Meigen, 1804) – syn. *Megaselia heracleellae* (Bouché, 1834) – Cosmopolitan. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Sarajevo (Strobl, 1900 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *rufipes* Fall. [sic!]), “Grotte Gorednica” = Gradnica Cave (Bezzi, 1911), “kleine Höhle bei Trebinje, Vrechovina dolinama”/Trebinje (Schmitz, 1919); Šnjetica pećina, 3.5 km NE Kifino Selo, Nevesinje; Šehina pećina, Blagaj, Mostar (Séguy, 1963); Schmitz, 1928, 1929; Disney, 1991; Bulgaria: Bulgaria (Drensky, 1934 as *Phora incrossata* [sic!], see Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), West Danube Plain, Predbalkan Mts, North Black Sea Coast, Central Stara Planina Mts, Lyulin Mt (Langourov, 2001), Sofia Plain (Nedelkov, 1912 as *Aphiochaeta rufipes* (Meigen) and *A. heracleellae* (Bouché); Langourov, 2001), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001, 2021), Rila Mts (Schmitz, 1953), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Strandzha Mt (Langourov,

- 2001); Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1937), Zadar (Strobl, 1902, 1904 as *Phora rufipes* Fall. [sic!]), Hvar (Strobl, 1902, 1904 as *Phora rufipes* Fall. [sic!]; Schmitz, 1919), Zagreb, Osijek, Bakar (Langhoffer, 1919), Plitvice (Coe, 1956), Mljet Island, Šipan Island, Lisac National Park (Schmitz, 1919); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991; Greece: Corfu Island (Schmitz, 1924b); Italy: “Höhle di Prosecco” = Grotta Gigante, N Trieste (Schmitz, 1919), Nabrežina/Aurisina (Funk & Graffe, 1895); Montenegro: Županska pećina, Lubnica (Berane); Pećina na Golubinja kod Plevanja (Séguy, 1963); North Macedonia: Krushevo (Langourov, 1999), Dihovo (Kiprijanovska et al, 2019); Romania: Băile Herculane (Kowarz, 1873; Thalhammer, 1899 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *rufipes* Meigen), Orșova (Kowarz, 1873), Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899 both as *Phora pulicaria* var. *rufipes* Meigen and *P. pulicaria* var. *heracleellae* (Bouche)), Tășnad, Sibiu Mt (Thalhammer, 1899 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *rufipes* Meigen and *P. pulicaria* var. *heracleellae* (Bouche)), Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *heracleellae* (Bouche)), Azuga (Fleck, 1904 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *rufipes* Fall. [sic!]), “Plasa Aiud: Râmetz [= Râmeț], Pesterea dela Curmătură Pleasei; Plasa Vascău: Măgura, Pesterea dela Măgura” (Leruth, 1941), Dobruddza (Langourov, 2001).
187. *Megaselia rupestris* Schmitz, 1934 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
188. *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew, 1866) – Cosmopolitan. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Greece: Serres (Langourov, 2004b); Serbia: Obedska bara (Langourov, 2004b).
189. *Megaselia scutellaris* (Wood, 1909) – syn. *Megaselia scutellariformis* (Schmitz, 1926) – Holarctic. Albania: Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Disney, 1991; Bosnia-Herzegovina: “Beretina pecina, Herceg.” (Schmitz, 1919); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Bulgaria: Bulgaria (Schmitz, 1953 as *M. scutellariformis* (Schmitz)), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Croatia: Jasenak, Brušane/Velebit Mts (Schmitz, 1924b); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a as *M. scutellaris* (Wood) and *M. scutellariformis* (Schmitz)); Disney, 1991 (former Yugoslavia).
190. *Megaselia sepulchralis* (Lundbeck, 1920) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
191. *Megaselia sericata* Schmitz, 1935 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
192. *Megaselia setulipalpis* Schmitz, 1938 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
193. *Megaselia sicaria* (Colyer, 1962) – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962 as *Plastophora*; Disney, 1991).
194. *Megaselia simplex* (Wood, 1910) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
195. *Megaselia simulans* (Wood, 1912) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Romania: Mehadia, Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1957b); Disney, 1991.
196. *Megaselia sordida* (Zetterstedt, 1838) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
197. *Megaselia spinata* (Wood, 1910) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
198. *Megaselia spinicincta* (Wood, 1910) – West-palaearctic. Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1924b), Reci (Schmitz, 1953).
199. *Megaselia spinigera* (Wood, 1908) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a (as *Plastophora*); Disney, 1991.
200. *Megaselia stichata* (Lundbeck, 1920) – West-palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
201. *Megaselia stigmatica* (Schmitz, 1920) – West-palaearctic. Greece: Disney, 1991.
202. *Megaselia striolata* Schmitz, 1940 – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
203. *Megaselia styloprocta* (Schmitz, 1921) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov,

- 2021); Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a as *Plastophora*).
204. *Megaselia subconvexa* (Lundbeck, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
205. *Megaselia subfraudulenta* Schmitz, 1933 – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b as *M. stichata* (Lundbeck), misidentification). Here is reported as new for the Balkan Peninsula.
206. *Megaselia subnudipennis* (Schmitz, 1919) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Băile Homorod (Schmitz, 1953).
207. *Megaselia subpleuralis* (Wood, 1909) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Reci (Schmitz, 1953).
208. *Megaselia subtumida* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
209. *Megaselia superciliata* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); North Macedonia: Prespa Lake (Coe, 1956; Schmitz & Beyer, 1974); Disney, 1991; Langourov, 1999; Romania: Aiud (Schmitz, 1953); Disney, 1991.
210. *Megaselia sylvatica* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: North Black Sea Coast, Varna (Schmitz, 1953), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a as *Megaselia latior* Schmitz, misidentification).
211. *Megaselia tabida* Colyer, 1956 – Endemic. North Macedonia: Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Colyer, 1956; Coe, 1956; Schmitz & Beyer, 1965b); Disney, 1991; Langourov, 1999.
212. *Megaselia tama* (Schmitz, 1926) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
213. *Megaselia tarsalis* (Wood, 1910) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Greece: Corfu Island (Schmitz, 1924b, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); North Macedonia: Prespa Lake, Oteshevo (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1999.
214. *Megaselia tarsella* (Lundbeck, 1921) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Gura Râului (Pârvu, 2001).
215. *Megaselia tarsicia* Schmitz, 1926 – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
216. *Megaselia tenebricola* Schmitz, 1934 – European. Bulgaria: Predbalkan Mts (Langourov, 2001), Vitosha (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Romania: Scărișoara, Câmpeni, Corobana Mândrutzului (Leruth, 1941).
217. *Megaselia tergata* (Lundbeck, 1920) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b).
218. *Megaselia thalhammeri* Schmitz, 1935 – Euro-Mediterranean. Bosnia-Herzegovina: Travnik (Schmitz, 1935a, 1957a; Strobl, 1898, 1900 as *Phora pulicaria* var. *pumila*, partim; Disney, 1991); Schmitz, 1940a, 1941a; North Macedonia: Prespa Lake (Coe, 1956); Schmitz, 1957a, Langourov, 1999.
219. *Megaselia trichorrhoea* (Schmitz, 1921) – Westpalaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Disney, 1991; Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956 as *M. (A.) trichorrhoea* [sic!]); Schmitz & Beyer, 1965a; Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Prespa Lake (Coe, 1956); Schmitz & Beyer, 1965a; Langourov, 1999.
220. *Megaselia tumida* (Wood, 1909) – Westpalaearctic. Bosnia-Herzegovina: “Eliashöhle bei Trebinje” [= Ilijina Pećina] (Schmitz, 1919); Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Plitvice (Coe, 1956).
221. *Megaselia uliginosa* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
222. *Megaselia unichaeta* Colyer, 1962 – Endemic. Slovenia: Postojna (Colyer, 1962; Schmitz & Delage, 1981; Disney, 1991).
223. *Megaselia unicolor* (Schmitz, 1919) – Palearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).
224. *Megaselia variana* Schmitz, 1926 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Mošunje, Stalak (Schmitz, 1924b as *Aphiochaeta variabilis* (Wood)), Plitvice (Coe, 1956); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a; Schmitz & Beyer, 1974; Disney, 1991; Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b as *A. variabilis* (Wood)).

225. *Megaselia verna* Schmitz, 1932 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001).
226. *Megaselia vernalis* (Wood, 1909) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Romania: Leordina, Maramureş Mts (Duşa, 1974); Bârsa Groşetului (Pârvu, 2001).
227. *Megaselia verralli* (Wood, 1910) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Sofia (Schmitz, 1953, 1958a), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Greece: Crete Island (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1958a; Schmitz & Delage, 1981); Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Galichitsa Mt/Ohrid Lake (Coe, 1956); Langourov, 1999; Slovenia: Laibach [= Ljubljana] (Schmitz, 1958a); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a.
228. *Megaselia vestita* (Wood, 1914) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
229. *Megaselia virilis* (Schmitz, 1919) – European. Romania: Gura Râului (Pârvu, 2001).
230. *Megaselia woodi* (Lundbeck, 1922) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
231. *Megaselia xanthozona* (Strobl, 1892) – Palaeartic-Afrotropical. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); North Macedonia: Baba Mt (Langourov, 1999); Romania: “Laduscher Bergbäche gegen den Cindrel” [Cindrel Mt] (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899), Frumoasa (Schmitz, 1924b), Ciceu (Schmitz, 1953), Eşelniţa (Duşa, 1970), Munţii Călimani, V. Lomaş (Harghita), Borsec, Tulgheş, Bradu (Neamţ) (Duşa, 1974); Disney, 1991.
232. *Megaselia zonata* (Zetterstedt, 1838) – European. Romania: Frumoasa (Schmitz, 1924b).
233. *Menoziola schmitzi* (Menozzi, 1921) – Euro-Mediterranean species. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Rijeka (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1941a); Disney, 1991.
234. *Metopina braueri* (Strobl, 1880) – Westpalaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
235. *Metopina crassinervis* Schmitz, 1920 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
236. *Metopina galeata* (Haliday, 1833) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021); Greece: Disney, 1991; Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a); Romania: Dubova, Berzaska, Plavişeviţa (near Dubova), Arcalia, Turda Băi, Şura Mare (Sibiu) (Duşa, 1970), Bradu (Neamţ) (Duşa, 1974).
237. *Metopina heselhausi* Schmitz, 1914 – Palaeartic-Afrotropical. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Greece: Disney, 1991; Romania: Borşa (Maramureş), Ruscova (Maramureş), Dealul Ştefăniţei (Bistriţa Năsăud) (Duşa, 1974).
238. *Metopina oligoneura* (Mik, 1867) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
239. *Metopina perpusilla* (Six, 1878) – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Croatia (Schmitz, 1928 as *Metopina galeata* (Haliday), misidentification; Schmitz, 1940b, 1941a).
240. *Metopina pileata* Schmitz, 1936 – West-palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Greece: Disney, 1991.
241. *Metopina ulrichi* Disney, 1979 – Westpalaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
242. *Obscuriphora sheppardi* Disney, 1986 – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010).
243. *Peromitra carinifrons* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
244. *Peromitra incrassata* (Meigen, 1830) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: “Sljeme” [Sljeme Peak, Medvednica Mt] (Langhoffer, 1919).
245. *Phalacrotophora berlinensis* Schmitz, 1920 – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b); Romania: Turnu Roşu (Schmitz, 1924b).
246. *Phalacrotophora fasciata* (Fallen, 1823) – Palaeartic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Italy: “Nel bosco di Farneto” = Farneto wood park, Trieste (Funk & Graffe, 1895); Montenegro: “Grotte de Gradje”, Đalovići/Djalovici (Séguy, 1963).
247. *Phalacrotophora pictofasciata* Schmitz, 1919 – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b); Romania: Mehadia (Schmitz, 1919, 1928, 1929, 1941a, 1953; Disney, 1991).

248. *Phora atra* (Meigen, 1804) – syn. *Phora aterrima* (Fabricius, 1794) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Greece: Disney, 1991; Croatia: Zagreb, Sljeme, Vinodol, Lokve, Bakar, Orehovica, Senj (Langhoffer, 1919 as *P. aterrima* F.), Novi [= Novi Vinodolski] (Schmitz, 1924b as *P. aterrima* F.), Rijeka (Strobl, 1893; Thalhammer, 1899 both as *Trineura aterrima* F.; Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b as *P. aterrima* F.); Schmitz, 1955; Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Osogovska Mt, Kitka Mt, Skopje, Galichitsa Mt (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Măgura Peak, Cindrel Mt, Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895 as *T. aterrima* F.), Sibiu Mt, Băile Herculane (Thalhammer, 1899 as *T. aterrima* F.), Ada Kaleh (former island in the Danube River, now under the water), Plavișevița (near Dubova), Băile Herculane (Dușa, 1970 as *P. aterrima* F.), Tg. Ocna, V. Uzului; Ticău (Maramureș) (Dușa, 1974 as *P. aterrima* F.), Malu, Giurgiu (Pârnu, 2005).
249. *Phora dubia* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
250. *Phora edentata* Schmitz, 1920 – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Croatia: Schmitz, 1955; Disney, 1991.
251. *Phora hamata* Schmitz, 1927 – European. Bulgaria: Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Romania: Malu, Giurgiu (Pârnu, 2005).
252. *Phora holosericea* Schmitz, 1920 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Kostinbrod (Langourov, 2004b), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Greece: Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Kitka Mt (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Baia Sprie (Schmitz, 1924b), Vișeu de Mijloc, Maramureș (Dușa, 1974); Disney, 1991.
253. *Phora horrida* Schmitz, 1920 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
254. *Phora penicillata* Schmitz, 1920 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Romania: Bucegi Mts: Cabana Zănoaga, Cheile Zănoagei, Peștera, Cabana Padina; Sinaia (Dușa, 1970), Pasul Prislop; Com. Șesuri (Suceava) (Dușa, 1974).
255. *Phora pubipes* Schmitz, 1920 – Palaearctic-Oriental. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Bosnia-Herzegovina: Jablanica (Strobl, 1898, 1900 as *Trineura aterrima* Mg. [sic!]); Romania: Târgu Ocna, Valea Uzului (Dușa, 1974).
256. *Phora stictica* Meigen, 1830 – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Vaganjski Vrh Peak/Velebit Mt (Schmitz, 1955); Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Baba Mt (Langourov, 1999); Romania: Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895), Sibiu Mt (Thalhammer, 1899), Retezat Mts (Schmitz, 1955), Eșelnița, Mehedinți (Dușa, 1970); Disney, 1991.
257. *Phora tincta* Schmitz, 1920 – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Croatia: Jasenak (Schmitz, 1924b); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1955; Disney, 1991; Slovenia: “Krain” (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1955); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
258. *Phora velutina* Meigen, 1830 – European. Croatia: Zagreb (Langhoffer, 1919); Romania: Rodna Mts (Schmitz, 1924a).
259. *Plectanocnema nudipes* (Becker, 1901) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
260. *Pseudacteon brevicauda* Schmitz, 1925 – European. Slovenia: Disney, 2000.
261. *Pseudacteon fennicus* Schmitz, 1927 – European. Bulgaria: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Slovenia: “Rokovo Dolina, River Rak” [= Rakov Škocjan] (Disney, 2000).
262. *Pseudacteon formicarum* (Verrall, 1877) – Palaearctic. Romania: Berzaska, Plavișevița (near Dubova), Ogradena, Mera (Dușa, 1970).
263. *Pseudacteon lundbecki* Schmitz, 1924 – European. Slovenia: “Rokovo Dolina, River Rak” [= Rakov Škocjan] (Disney, 2000).
264. *Spiniphora bergenstammi* (Mik, 1864) – Subcosmopolitan. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021); Greece: Crete Island, Greece (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b);

- Disney, 1991; Croatia: Dalmatia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b); Disney, 1991; Italy: Gorizia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b); Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Skopje (Langourov, 1999).
265. *Spiniphora brevipalpis* (Schmitz, 1935) – Endemic. Cyprus: Cyprus Island (Schmitz, 1935b, 1940a: “Kreta” [error!], 1940b, 1941b; Disney, 1991).
266. *Spiniphora dorsalis* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: Croatia (Becker, 1901), Sljeme (Langhoffer, 1919); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b; Disney, 1991; North Macedonia: Shar Mts (Langourov, 1999).
267. *Spiniphora jugorum* (Schmitz, 1924) – Euro-Caucasian. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Montenegro: Durmitor Mt (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b); Disney, 1991; Langourov, 2004a.
268. *Spiniphora maculata* (Meigen, 1830) – syn. *Spiniphora helicivora* (Dufour, 1841) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c); Croatia: Zadar (Strobl, 1902, 1904), “Lussin” = Lošinj Island (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b all as *Paraspiniphora/Spiniphora helicivora* (Dufour)); Disney, 1991; Italy: Gorizia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1941b all as *Paraspiniphora/Spiniphora helicivora* (Dufour)); Disney, 1991.
269. *Spiniphora punctipennis* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Mediterranean. Greece: “Canea” [= Chania, Crete Island] (Schmitz, 1924b as *Paraspiniphora maculata* (Meigen), see Schmitz, 1935b, 1953).
270. *Spiniphora strobli* (Becker, 1901) – European. Romania: Postăvarul Massif (Strobl, 1895); Băile Herculane, Bakar (Thalhammer, 1899); Rodna Mts (Schmitz, 1924a, 1953).
271. *Stichillus coronatus* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2004b as *Peromitra germanica* (Schmitz), misidentification; material checked: Sofia, Hladilnika District, 42.653217°N, 23.322168°E, 610 m, 25.vi–25.vii.1997, 1 ♂). Here is reported as new for the Balkan Peninsula.
272. *Triphleba antricola* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Bosnia-Herzegovina: “Grotte Gorednica” = Gradnica Cave (Bezzi, 1911 as *Phora aptina* Schiner, misidentification; Schmitz, 1919b), “Höhle bei Gluta Smohva”, caves near Trebinje, Baba pecina b. Zavala = Vjetrenica Cave, Ivanica Cave (Schmitz, 1919b), Novakuša/ La grotte de Starina Novak, Bisina, Nevesinje (Séguy, 1963); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1943; Bulgaria: East Danube Plane, Predbalkan Mts, Western Stara Planina Mts, Central Stara Planina Mts, Eastern Stara Planina Mts, Vitosha Mt, Osogovska Mts, Pirin Mts, Western Rhodope Mts, Eastern Rhodope Mts, Derventski Hills, Strandzha Mt (Langourov, 2001, 2004c, 2010, 2021; Hazelton, 1970); Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1937, 1938); Greece: Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2001); Italy: “Grotte di Prosecco” = Grotta Gigante, N Trieste (Bezzi, 1914 as *P. aptina* Schiner, misidentification; Schmitz, 1943); Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1943; Romania: Höhle Batrina [= Bătrâna] (Schmitz, 1924b), “Plasa Abrud: Sohodol [Sohodol, Abrud, Alba], Pesterea Lucia mare; Plasa Aiud: Râmetz [= Râmeț], Pesterea dela Curmătură Pleasei; Plasa Vascău: Fânatze [= Fânațe], Pesterea dela Fânatze; Băitza, Pesterea dela Varnitza; Sighistel, Dracoaia; Pesterea de sus dela Corbesti, Pesterea dela Corbasta; Plasa Câmpeni: Scărișoara [Scărișoara, Câmpeni], Huda dela Politza, Corobana Mândrutzului” (Leruth, 1941), Peștera de la Fânațe, Munții (Mts) Bihor (Schmitz, 1943), Dobrudzha (Langourov, 2001); Schmitz, 1940b, 1943; Serbia: Petnica Cave (Schmitz, 1919b); Slovenia: “Nanos Höhle” = Postojna Cave (Schmitz, 1919b).
273. *Triphleba aptina* (Schiner, 1853) – European. Bosnia-Herzegovina: “Grotte Gorednica” = Gradnica Cave, Vilina pecina u. Napode (Schmitz, 1919), Govednica Cave, near Banja Stijena, Prača, close to Sarajevo, Jama Cankarica bei Goranci/Cabalja Mt (Schmitz, 1943); Bulgaria: Western Stara Planina Mts (Langourov, 2001); Croatia: Velika Spilja (cave)/Mljet Island, Štirovača Cave/Velebit Mts, “Höhle am Lisac, Krivosije – Geb. Suddalmatien” (Schmitz, 1919); Montenegro: Matijesevica, S. W. Montenegro (Schmitz, 1919b), Kaparica pecina, Höhle am Kabao (Schmitz, 1943); Slovenia: Monte Nanos, “Adelsberger Grotte” = Postojna Cave (Schiner,

- 1853; Schmitz, 1919b), Kozja pečina/Carniola (Schmitz, 1919).
274. *Triphleba autumnalis* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).
275. *Triphleba bicornuta* (Strobl, 1910) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt, Rila Mts (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021).
276. *Triphleba citreiformis* (Becker, 1901) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
277. *Triphleba distinguenda* (Strobl, 1892) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997), Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2010); Montenegro: Bjelasitsa Mt (Langourov, 2004a).
278. *Triphleba dudai* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021).
279. *Triphleba gracilis* (Wood, 1907) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021).
280. *Triphleba hyalinata* (Meigen, 1830) – syn. *Phora perennis* Meigen, 1838 – European. Bulgaria: Central Stara Planina Mts, Sofia Plain (Langourov, 2001), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2001; Langourov et al., 2014, Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2001; Langourov, 2004c); Italy: Trieste (Funk & Graffe, 1895 as *Phora perennis* Meigen); Romania: Sasca Română (Schmitz, 1924b as *Trupheoneura perennis* (Meigen), 1953).
281. *Triphleba hypopygialis* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
282. *Triphleba inaequalis* Schmitz, 1943 – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021).
283. *Triphleba intermedia* (Malloch, 1908) – West-palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Western Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2010), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004c); Romania: Liborajdea, Caraș-Severin (Dușa, 1970).
284. *Triphleba longifurcata* (Schmitz, 1922) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
285. *Triphleba lugubris* (Meigen, 1830) – Holarctic-Oriental. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021); Croatia: St. Roumuald cave/Lim Channel Istria (Pax, 1937 as *Diploneura* [sic!] *lugubris* (Meigen)).
286. *Triphleba nudipalpis* (Becker, 1901) – Palaearctic. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Kresna Gorge (Langourov & Sakalian, 2001).
287. *Triphleba opaca* (Meigen, 1830) – Palaearctic. Albania: Disney, 1991; Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Langourov, 2021); Italy: Trieste (Funk & Graffe, 1895), Gorizia (Schmitz, 1928, 1929, 1940b, 1943); Disney, 1991; Romania: Azuga (Fleck, 1904); Sasca Montană (Schmitz, 1924b); Disney, 1991; former Yugoslavia: Disney, 1991.
288. *Triphleba pachyneurella* (Schmitz, 1919) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
289. *Triphleba palposa* (Zetterstedt, 1848) – Holarctic. Romania: Cisnădioara (Strobl, 1895; Thalhammer, 1899 as “Miebelsberg” [error!]).
290. *Triphleba papillata* (Wingate, 1906) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov et al., 2014; Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mountains (Langourov, 2004c).
291. *Triphleba trinervis* (Becker, 1901) – Holarctic. Bulgaria: Sofia Plain (Beschovski & Langourov, 1997; Nedelkov, 1912 as *Phora opaca* Meigen, misidentification; Langourov, 2004b), Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).
292. *Triphleba tumidula* (Schmitz, 1918) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021), Eastern Rhodope Mts (Langourov, 2004c).
293. *Triphleba vitrea* (Wood, 1906) – European. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
294. *Triphleba withersi* Disney, 1992 – Mediterranean. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
295. *Tubicera lichtwardti* Schmitz, 1920 – Mediterranean. Bulgaria: Vitosha Mt (Langourov, 2021).
- *Musca festinans* Scopoli, 1763: Entom. carniolica: 349 (*Musca*). Type-locality: “Carniola” [Dalmatia] (Slovenia). First phorid ever described. Nomen dubium.

The distribution of the species established so far by country is as follows: Albania (4 species/2 genera),

Bosnia and Herzegovina (18/5), Bulgaria (230/23), Croatia (70/14), Cyprus (2/2), Greece (30/9), Montenegro (50/10), North Macedonia (40/4), Romania (103/13), Serbia (12/3), Slovenia (36/6), only the Balkan part of Italy (14/6). Conclusions cannot be drawn from the given data, and this only shows where the studies have been more intensive and how poor our knowledge of the family is in this part of Europe.

Judging by the number of species in European countries with relatively well-studied scuttle fly fauna (such as the United Kingdom, where 358 species have been reported (Chandler, 2025)), we can speculate that their number on the Balkan Peninsula should exceed 400 species.

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the author, reviewers, or subject editor. As a member of the editorial board Mario Langourov recused himself from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Mario Langourov: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, resources, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

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